

Exploring the Symbiotic Relationship between Dialectics and Dialogical Approaches to Education in the Era of Artificial Intelligence: A Philosophical Perspective

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Introduction

Dialectic and dialogue are commonly recognized as distinct approaches to learning and intellectual development, with their relationship being a topic of debate within the international academic community. The central question revolves around whether meaning is achieved through the integration of different perspectives (dialectic) or through the emergence of diverse perspectives (dialogue). Advocates of the dialectical approach argue that meaning is constructed through the synthesis of diverse perspectives, while proponents of the dialogical approach assert that meaning arises from the differences in perspectives. However, this relationship is complex. I contend that these approaches are interdependent and mutually evolving. Unity cannot exist without differences, and differences are not recognized unless we strive to unite various perspectives. The unity of different perspectives is provisional, and different interpretations of the unified perspectives give rise to new perspectives, which are subject to continual (re)unification. Epistemologically, I understand dialectics as a method of reasoning employed to explore truth through dialogue (Nikulin, 2010). Dialectic and dialogue are inseparable; one cannot exist without the other. There appears to be a symbiotic relationship between dialectic and dialogue, and exploring this relationship may transform educational practices that are often divided into either dialectic or dialogue. Transforming educational practices entails creating learning environments that are profoundly participatory, interactive, and collaborative. This approach fosters shared understanding, cultivates agency, and promotes the co-development of individuals as diversely competent beings. Through dialogue and dialectical engagement, learners participate in collective knowledge construction, thereby empowering themselves to take ownership of their educational journeys while embracing a multitude of perspectives and capabilities. Such an approach nurtures holistic growth, equipping individuals to navigate and to contribute meaningfully to an interconnected and complex world.

In this paper, I argue for the symbiotic relationship between dialectic and dialogue by drawing on the works of several scholars (for example, Buber, 1944; Mirković, 1980; Baxter & Montgomery, 1996; Nikulin, 2006; Douglas, 2010; Hegel, 2018; Dafermos, 2018), who provide insights into the complex, contradictory, and reconciliatory relationship between the two concepts. I also attempt to discuss how dialectic and dialogue can be construed in the era of artificial intelligence systems, with which human actors can have an endless dialogue about any topic of interest. Before engaging in the philosophical debates on this topic, I will first present distinct discussions regarding dialectic and dialogue. Following this, I will examine the symbiotic relationship between the two and their application in educational practices. This exploration will include an

assessment of the impact of AI on both dialectic and dialogue. Finally, I will provide a concluding note on the interconnectedness of dialogue and dialectic.

Dialectic

Dialectic traces its origins back to ancient Greece, where it was developed by philosophers such as Socrates, Plato, and Aristotle. The term “*dialectic*” is derived from the Greek word “*dialektikḗ*,” which means “*art of conversation*.” Billig (1987) suggests that the Sophist Protagoras was the first to assert that every issue has two opposing lines of argument. Views, opinions, or attitude exist where there is a context of controversy and contradictions. However, the Greek philosophers most closely associated with dialectical methods are Socrates and Plato, who viewed dialectic as the pursuit of truth through reasoned discussion and the resolution of contradictory arguments, as illustrated masterfully in Plato’s Socratic dialogues. Plato held dialectic in such high regard that he proposed in his republic that philosophers receive training in it (Baxter & Montgomery, 1996).

According to Kahn (1979), Heraclitus, an ancient Greek philosopher born around 535 BCE in Ephesus, was renowned for his philosophical contributions centered on the concept of change and flux in the natural world. He is often referred to as the “Philosopher of Change.” Heraclitus proposed that everything in the universe is in a constant state of transformation. Kahn translates Heraclitus as saying,

One cannot step twice into the same river, nor can one grasp any moral substance in a stable condition, but it scatters and again gathers: it forms and dissolves, and approaches, and departs.... [A]s they step into the same river, others and still other waters flow upon them. (Kahn, 1979, p. 52)

Although dialectical elements can be identified in the writings of mediæval and early modern philosophers like Augustine, Aquinas, Descartes, Spinoza, Kant, and Rousseau, Mirković (1980) argues that dialectics became a distinct philosophical worldview in the nineteenth century through the works of the German philosopher Hegel and his student Karl Marx. In Hegelian-Marxian dialectics, the influence of Heraclitus’s dialectical view of the universe was crucial.

Baxter & Montgomery (1996) state that Hegel was dedicated to philosophical idealism, positing that human reason, or thought, serves as a creative force underlying both the natural world and the driving force of human history. His intellectual endeavors are evident in his attempts to formulate a philosophy of consciousness development and, by extension, an ontology of reality, conceptualizing reality as a manifestation of mind. Each concrete entity exists within a totality defined by what it is not, emphasizing constant motion, development, and change.

Hegel’s perspective on truth involves the realization of the interconnectedness and fluidity of phenomena, a concept he terms “*becoming*.” Criticizing the prevailing philosophy of his era, Hegel rejected the representation of phenomena as autonomous, finite, and fixed entities, referred to as “*being*.” Instead, he proposed that our perception of phenomena is organized around the principle of “*Nothing*,” signifying that our understanding of something relies on an awareness of its negation. This understanding acknowledges that everything undergoes continuous flux and transitions to new forms through the interplay of opposing forces. Consciousness, according to

Hegel, is the synthesis of Being, Nothing, and/or Becoming—an understanding that a phenomenon and its opposite merge, and each immediately vanishes due to the presence of the other (Hegel, 2018). Hegel considered Becoming a higher truth, a deeper reality than the static superficialities of Being, whether applied to the development of individual consciousness or the evolution of societal knowledge. He viewed Becoming as the teleological unfolding of the idea or *Spirit (Geist)*—the immanent and rational order of the universe. The theological implications of *Geist* are evident, as Hegel envisioned Becoming as an evolutionary process through which humanity comprehends God’s plan for the universe.

Contradiction, arising from the interplay of Being and Nothing, was not perceived by Hegel as a negative phenomenon, but rather as essential for achieving the heightened consciousness of Becoming. However, it is important to note that Hegel’s philosophy and theology primarily revolve around the consciousness of the mind, with indirect implications for social experiences. Hegel asserted that ideas hold precedence and shape the world (Gordon, 2022), emphasizing the need for a thorough understanding of ideas before their effective implementation into the material realm.

Karl Marx undertook the task of formulating a dialectics of social experiences, building upon Hegel’s dialectics as the groundwork for his own theory, termed dialectical materialism (Baxter & Montgomery, 1996; Dafermos, 2018). However, Marx diverged from Hegel’s idealism and embraced a materialistic interpretation of reality. He argued that the ideal is a mere reflection of the material world shaped by human activity, in contrast to Hegel’s notion of the ideal as an existing concept of the mind (Marx, 1961, cited in Baxter & Montgomery, 1996). According to Marx, consciousness is rooted in the actuality of people’s existence rather than in ideas independent of the material world, as posited by Hegel.

Central to everyday life is the process of production, where individuals engage in activities to satisfy fundamental needs such as the acquisition of food, drink, shelter, and clothing. This organization of production gives rise to the division of labor, resulting in alienation among workers due to their fragmented control over productive activities. Consequently, this division of labor leads to exploitation, generating private property and capital for the ruling class. Despite these challenges, humans possess the capacity for consciousness, enabling them to reflect on their oppressive circumstances and create new material conditions that liberate them from such oppressions.

Mirkovic (1980) argues that Marx was the first scholar to systematically incorporate a social scientific perspective into the study of dialectics. Marx transposed Hegel’s dialectics from the realm of the mind into the tangible practices of society. Rather than disregarding consciousness, Marx reimagined it as a social phenomenon. His contribution to the study of dialectics was significant, as he was the first to apply a social scientific approach to this field. Prior to Marx, dialectics had largely been confined to the mind, as expounded by Hegel. However, Marx revolutionized this approach by moving the dialectical method from abstract thought to the concrete practices and dynamics of society. In doing so, he sought to ground dialectical thought in the material conditions and social relations that constitute human existence.

One of Marx's significant departures from Hegel's dialectics was his emphasis on the material and social dimensions of human experience. While Hegel's dialectics predominantly focused on the evolution of ideas and consciousness, Marx redirected attention to the material conditions of production, exchange, and class relations. In this manner, Marx aimed to illustrate that dialectical processes are not merely abstract concepts but are profoundly rooted in the concrete realities of social existence.

Moreover, Marx's reimagining of consciousness as a social phenomenon was a pivotal contribution to the study of dialectics. Rather than dismissing or downplaying the role of consciousness, Marx recognized its significance within the social fabric. Consciousness, in Marx's view, is not an isolated or individualistic phenomenon, but is shaped and influenced by the broader social and historical context in which individuals are situated. This understanding of consciousness as a social product has profound implications for how we comprehend human agency, ideology, and the dynamics of social change.

In essence, Marx's incorporation of a social scientific perspective into the study of dialectics laid the groundwork for a more holistic and materialist understanding of human history and society. By shifting the focus from abstract metaphysical concepts to the concrete realities of social life, Marx's approach has had a lasting impact on fields such as sociology, anthropology, and critical theory. It has also opened up new avenues for exploring the interplay between structure and agency, power and resistance, and the complexities of social transformation.

Mirkovic's (1980) assertion that Marx was a trailblazer in systematically integrating a social scientific perspective into the study of dialectics is well-founded. Marx's reconfiguration of dialectical thought not only expanded the horizons of this intellectual tradition, but also enriched our understanding of the intricate interconnections between thought, society, and history. As we continue to grapple with the complexities of contemporary social life, Marx's insights into dialectics serve as a compelling reminder of the enduring relevance of his contributions to social theory and praxis.

Baxter & Montgomery (1996) observe that dialectics has evolved into broader interpretations: ontological and epistemological perspectives. Dialectics as ontology involves the comprehension of reality as a dynamic interplay characterized by the conflict of opposing forces. In this context, it emphasizes the inherent dynamism and transformative nature of the world, where conflicting elements engage in a perpetual process of change and development. On the other hand, dialectics as epistemology constitutes a method of reasoning that seeks understanding through the collision of divergent arguments. This approach to dialectics focuses on the process of acquiring knowledge and insights through the confrontation and synthesis of opposing viewpoints. It implies a methodical engagement with contradictory perspectives, fostering a deeper and more nuanced understanding of complex phenomena.

These dual facets of dialectics, whether viewed as an ontological framework or an epistemological approach, contribute to a comprehensive understanding of the dynamic and interconnected nature of reality, both in terms of its inherent characteristics and the methods employed in the pursuit of knowledge. The interplay between ontological and epistemological dimensions enriches the

philosophical discourse surrounding dialectics, offering insights into the intricate relationships and transformations that shape our perception of the world.

In my opinion, the process of attempting to synthesize ideas does not simply involve closing off existing ideas, but rather allows for the emergence of new ideas and the expansion of possibilities for dialogue. When we engage in the act of synthesis, we are not merely seeking to reach a conclusion or find a single solution. Instead, we are opening ourselves up to the potential for new connections, insights, and perspectives to emerge. By bringing together different ideas, perspectives, and information, we create the opportunity for a richer and more nuanced understanding of a given topic or issue. This process of synthesis is essential for fostering innovation, creativity, and critical thinking. It enables us to move beyond the limitations of binary thinking and explore the complexities and nuances of the world around us. Through synthesis, we can uncover new possibilities, challenge assumptions, and generate novel approaches to solving problems. In this way, synthesis serves as a catalyst for intellectual growth and the advancement of knowledge. It encourages us to embrace the inherent complexity of the world and to engage in open, inclusive, and dynamic dialogue that allows for the co-creation of new ideas and perspectives.

In the next section, I will discuss the phenomenon of dialogue.

Dialogue

Like dialectics, the genesis of dialogue traces back to the ancient Greek word for conversation. The term “*dialogue*” is etymologically rooted in the Greek words “*dia*” and “*logos*,” signifying “through” and “speech” respectively. The early documented instance of written dialogue is discerned in Plato’s philosophical writings, where he employed this format to delve into intricate ideas and arguments through the interactions of characters. This form of philosophical dialogue emerged as a prominent feature of ancient Greek intellectual life, with influential thinkers like Socrates, Aristotle, and others utilizing it as a means of inquiry and debate. Various kinds of dialogue, including political, philosophical, and dramatic forms, historically surfaced in Ancient Greece (Dafermos, 2018). Dialogue involves an exchange and the alternation of questions and answers.

According to Maranhao (1990), tracing back to Plato, dialogue persistently occupies a programmatically liminal position, characterized by its interstructural nature—existing between two states or conditions. It remains essentially unstructured, deliberately avoiding closure and finality, perpetually serving as a vehicle for reshaping old elements into new patterns (Turner, 1967, pp. 97-98, as cited in Maranhao, 1990, p. 47). Dialogue serves as a meeting ground, *communitas*, manifesting itself in diverse spontaneous and ritual modes of discourse, where nature and structure converge.

Maranhao (1990) discusses the significance of dialogue within the context of the modern hermeneutic tradition, drawing on the perspectives of scholars such as Gadamer, Ricœur, and Bakhtin. These scholars emphasize the interconnected nature of speech, highlighting its intertextual and interlocal dimensions. Plato’s dialogues, for instance, not only juxtapose ideas and concepts, but also involve interlocutors who represent both real and unreal beings. The focus of these dialogues is not on events and causality, but rather on understanding abstract concepts

such as justice, the good, and truth. The aim is to explore how these concepts can be articulated and comprehended more deeply. While Aristotle structured dialogues around dramatic plots and themes, reflecting temporal sequences, Plato's dialogues lack systematicity and definitive conclusions. However, scholars argue that Plato's dialogues exhibit varying degrees or different types of systematicity. Long (2013) asserts that Plato perceives philosophy as a process characterized by continuous questioning rather than by the provision of definitive answers; consequently, Plato's dialogues are designed to stimulate readers to engage in independent thought rather than merely assimilating the ideas of the authors. This approach mirrors Socrates' dialectical method, which entails the questioning and critical examination of ideas.

Moreover, Socrates, a central figure in these dialogues, often presents contradictory viewpoints, underscoring the fluid and dynamic nature of dialogue. This stands in contrast to Aristotle's view of dialectic as a method for testing propositions and establishing arguments. Overall, the tradition of dialogue as expounded by these scholars underscores its multifaceted and evolving nature, characterized by the blending and crossing of voices rather than the rigid delineation of positions.

According to Nikulin (2006), dialogue assumes the status of a distinctive form—a written emulation of oral discourse—without which human existence as individuals and the expression of selfhood would be unattainable. Aristotle, in his contributions to dialogue, introduced innovations that transitioned it from spontaneous live conversation towards a more rationalized literary genre. One such innovation is Aristotle's incorporation of a prooemion, which systematically employs an alternation of short rejoinders with extensive reasoned accounts, a method frequently utilized by Plato. Nikulin (2006) also references Martin Buber's categorization of dialogue into three types. The first type is real dialogue, regarded as the only one of genuine value, in which each participant seeks the other in their uniqueness, endeavoring to establish a "living" communication. Real dialogue can manifest through both words and silence. For Bakhtin, real dialogue represents the fundamental and classic form of speech, communication, and interaction. Technical dialogue emerges from the attempt to convey and exchange information, while monologue masquerading as dialogue involves individuals ostensibly addressing others but essentially speaking to themselves, futilely attempting to escape their selfhood.

Three modes of perceiving another person are outlined by Martin Buber (Nikulin, 2006). The first mode is observation (*Beobachten*), which entails the analysis of objective characteristics in the other. The second mode is contemplation or looking on (*Betrachten*), wherein one anticipates spontaneous revelations without deliberate pursuit. The third mode is penetration or in-becoming (*innewerden*), which occurs when the other communicates, thereby entering one's life through an appeal. Unlike the first two modes, this mode of perception does not seek to define the essence of the other, recognizing the potential inclusion of entities beyond human beings, such as animals, plants, or stones. The capacity for dialogue fundamentally characterizes the human being as one who possesses a voice or, more precisely, as a pure voice. Each speaking voice yearns to be heard, and every heard voice longs for a response, thereby illustrating the intrinsic desire for dialogue.

Mikhail Bakhtin, a prominent Russian intellectual renowned for his dialogic theory, is regarded by some as one of the most influential intellectual figures of the 20th century (Holquist, 2002). He critiqued the prevailing linguistic, literary, philosophical, and political theories of his time for their tendency to monologize human experience. Bakhtin (1984) aimed to challenge closed,

determinate, and totalizing concepts that obscured the open, unfinalizable, and heterogeneous nature of social life. His analysis particularly emphasized the literary genre of the novel as an exemplar of dialogic expression. The essence of dialogue lies in its simultaneous differentiation from and fusion with the other. Parties engaged in dialogue must integrate perspectives while preserving the uniqueness of individual viewpoints. In contrast to monologue, dialogue is characterized by multivocality, encompassing the presence of at least two distinct voices. Bakhtin (1981) posited that all processes arise from the contradictory unity of two opposing tendencies: the centripetal forces of unity and the centrifugal forces of difference. The multivocality of social reality emerges through the contradictory interplay of these centripetal and centrifugal forces.

The self is constructed in the ongoing interplay of the centripetal and the centrifugal. According to Bakhtin, the self is possible only in the fusion with another: “I achieve self-consciousness, I become myself only by revealing myself to another, through another and with another’s help.... Cutting oneself off, isolating oneself, closing oneself off, those are the basic reasons for loss of self” (Bakhtin, 1981, as quoted in Todorov, 1984, p.96). Self is constructed out of the two contradictory necessities—the need to connect with another (the centripetal force) and the simultaneous need to separate from the other (the centrifugal force). The centripetal and centrifugal dialogue is the indeterminate process in which the self is in a perpetual state of becoming, a consequence of the ongoing interplay between fusion with and separation from others.

The social life is an ongoing dynamic tension between forces of unity and difference, order and disorder. The interplay cannot be reduced to a single, static binary opposition: centripetal and centrifugal forces are multiple, varied, and everchanging in the immediate context of the moment. The tension between centripetal and centrifugal themes, beliefs, ideologies, and values takes concrete form in everyday interaction practices of social life.

The concept of chronotope is important in understanding the contexted nature of centripetal and centrifugal forces. Chronotope literally means “time-space” (Bakhtin 1981, p. 84), and the term captures the notion that everyday dialogue is enacted in a concrete temporal-spatial context. “Every entry into the sphere of meaning is accomplished only through the dates of chronotope” (Bakhtin, 1981, p. 258). Chronotopes both constrain and enable human dialogue. Chronotopes that have become standardized through shared meanings constrain the range of communicative events that are regarded as appropriate in those contexts. Technology as standardized chronotopes can limit the possibilities of dialogue. For example, a married couple might have a shared understanding that confrontational exchanges between them are inappropriately enacted in public settings or late in the evening when they are tired. A chronotope that serves as a common temporal-spatial locale for the enactment of certain communicative events has a chronotopic aura that facilitates those events. For example, candlelight and flowers might have an aura of romance for a couple that facilitates the enactment of intimacy. People shape their chronotopic landscape, and in turn their shared chronotopes influence the dialogues and meanings that can be sustained.

In alignment with Marx, Bakhtin viewed individual consciousness as a social process rather than the cognitive workings of an autonomous entity (Baxter & Montgomery, 1996). However, unlike Marx, Bakhtin did not confine his conceptualization of the social milieu to economic production. For Bakhtin, social reality encompasses all aspects of human experience constituted through communicative or symbolic practices. Consequently, Bakhtin’s understanding of consciousness

extends beyond class consciousness to include all foundations of conscious awareness concerning oneself and others.

Thus, dialogue is a fundamental aspect of human existence, providing the foundation for growth, understanding, and meaning making. It serves as the arena in which individuals navigate experiences, exchange ideas, and construct their understanding of the world. Beyond individual interactions, dialogue is pivotal to cultural and societal development. Through dialogue, communities negotiate values, address shared challenges, and envision collective futures. In this context, dialogue functions as both a method and an ethos, embodying a commitment to mutual respect, collaborative inquiry, and the co-creation of meaning. Dialectic complements dialogue by acting as a dynamic force that expands its scope, fostering critical thinking, analysis, and the examination of contrasting perspectives. This interplay between dialogue and dialectic creates a mutually reinforcing relationship, wherein each element shapes and enhances the other. Dialogue provides the contextual framework within which dialectic operates, while dialectic enriches dialogue by driving it towards greater depth, complexity, and understanding. Together, dialogue and dialectic form a symbiotic relationship that is essential for both individual growth and societal progress. Their interplay not only deepens collective understanding but also enables critical engagement with the world around us.

In the subsequent section, I will examine this symbiotic relationship in greater detail.

Symbiotic Relationship between Dialectic and Dialogue

From a philosophical standpoint, symbiosis transcends a mere biological association between different species. It is not simply defined as “any association between different species” or “persistent mutualism,” but rather as a profound interconnection that becomes “a source of new capabilities” and modes of existence (Douglas, 2010, pp 5-13). In its essence, symbiosis reflects the complex web of life, wherein the relationships among species are not static, but dynamic, revealing an ongoing dialogue between cooperation, coexistence, and competition. It underscores the intertwining of life in a manner that provides new insights into the nature of existence and relationality. Such symbiotic relationships may range from mutually beneficial to neutral or harmful. For instance, mutualism is exemplified in the relationship between bees and flowers, where both species derive benefits from pollination and nectar collection. Conversely, parasitism is observed in the interaction between ticks and mammals, with ticks benefiting from feeding on the mammals’ blood. Predation is illustrated by the relationship between lions and zebras, where the lion benefits from killing and consuming the zebra. These relationships can be extrapolated to human interactions in various contexts; however, this paper primarily draws inspirations from the conceptualization of symbiosis as mutual beneficialism and as a source of novel creativity and imagination, particularly in the context of the interplay between dialogue and dialectic.

However, the symbiotic relationship between dialectic and dialogue is often overlooked due to the varying orientations and appropriations of dialectic and dialogic worldviews, which align with the prevailing socio-political narratives in different societies. This oversight can also be attributed, in part, to a superficial understanding (though I do not claim a comprehensive understanding either) and the disciplinary siloing of these two approaches to learning and intellectual development.

Research indicates that the integration of dialogue and dialectic fosters active participation and promotes the creative process in learning and supervision (Gordon, 2022; Yerushalmi, 2024).

Tracing interconnected links between dialogue and dialectic to the Greek term for conversation, Fink (2012) posits that the literary genre of dialogue emerged through the ingenuity of Socrates' adherents, who sought to provide a written manifestation of dialectic. Dialogue embodies a conversational style of philosophical reasoning that necessitates the involvement of two individuals: the questioner and the respondent. The questioner prompts the respondent to assert a position, and subsequently subjects this assertion to scrutiny through a series of interrogative steps. The questioner aims to lead the respondent to refute the initial assertion through the process of addressing these questions. If successful, the respondent is refuted; otherwise, the initial assertion may endure, at least temporarily. A notable virtue of dialectic lies in the fact that the questioner is not obligated to possess expertise in the subject under discussion. This characteristic rendered the role of the questioner particularly suitable for Socrates, who famously asserted that his wisdom resided in acknowledging his lack of substantial knowledge on any given subject. The virtue of "holy insecurity" encapsulates a willingness to suspend assumptions, engage collaboratively in the exploration of alternative ideas, and permit new understandings to emerge. Within this framework, the binary of "either-or" is supplanted by the integrative approach of "both-and" wherein alternatives are synthesized, and complexity is embraced. This process culminates in apperception—a heightened awareness of all entities as interconnected and part of a larger whole (Scott, 2011). Scott further contends that this perspective embodies the essence of Buber's philosophy: an overarching consciousness of interconnectedness paired with a unifying apperception. To possess this virtue entails recognizing not only the relationships among the components within a system but also the dynamic interplay between oneself and others.

Dialectic, as explained by Cronenberg and Headley (2019), moves beyond the binary approach of absolute acceptance or rejection of a proposition or the competitive determination of the superiority of one participant's ideas. Instead, it is a dynamic process aimed at expanding knowledge, synthesizing ideas, and fostering improvement. Within this process, participants sequentially pose questions, identify contradictions within propositions, and collaboratively develop new perspectives, which remain provisional and open to further inquiry. This collective endeavor enables the exploration of diverse viewpoints, the scrutiny of relevant aspects, and the contemplation of alternatives. While deliberations may sometimes lead to an entirely new proposition, the dialectic process typically retains certain elements of the original proposition, ensuring continuity and openness to dialogue. The resultant propositions preserve characteristics of their predecessors while integrating new elements, potentially sourced from additional inputs, thereby contributing to a continuous evolution (Farjoun, 2018). Consequently, dialectics should not be perceived as a rigid process aimed at achieving a shared understanding; rather, it is a dialogic process of integrating diverse perspectives to reach a shared understanding at the moment of discourse.

According to Gordon (2022), the concept of dialogue has a longstanding presence in human interactions, predating recorded history. However, scholarly attention directed toward dialogue, as it is currently understood, has emerged more recently in comparison to the extensive focus on dialectic. Scott (2011) elaborates on Buber's concept of dialogue by identifying seven virtues that are essential to meaningful and transformative conversations. These virtues include *awareness*,

which involves focusing on the other, listening, and understanding their perspectives, while also being mindful of our own thoughts, feelings, and words. *Confirmation* refers to respecting the other as an equal and thoughtfully acknowledging their views, even in disagreement. *Empathic inclusion* involves connecting personally with the other's situation, allowing one to share their experiences. *Presence* emphasizes active engagement, where individuals respond authentically and commit to both learning from and expressing themselves to the other, while maintaining personal convictions and affirming the identity of their dialogue partner. Additionally, *openness* is the virtue of receptivity to new ideas and perspectives, remaining flexible and willing to expand one's views. *Mutuality* speaks to the shared responsibility of both participants in the dialogue, engaging in a reciprocal exchange that influences and shapes each other's understanding. Lastly, *trust* is fundamental, providing a foundation where individuals can be vulnerable and honest without fear of judgement or manipulation. Together, these virtues foster a dynamic, respectful, and productive dialogue, promoting both personal and collective growth.

Bakhtin, another advocate of dialogue, posited that one's identity and development are achievable only through relationships with others (Defermos, 2018). He envisioned a world composed of multiple voices and meanings, asserting that truth emerges through collective exploration and dialogue among interested parties. For Bakhtin, "voice" encompasses not only the individual's vocal expression but also theories, perspectives, or propositions. While he emphasized the importance of individual voices, Bakhtin also advocated for the merging of these voices to create a shared perspective (Baxter, 2004).

Although Bakhtin is often said to have opposed dialectics in the search for universal rationality, which might undermine the emergence of multiple voices (Matusov, 2011), Brandist (2002) suggests that Bakhtin may have contrasted dialogue with structuralism—specifically, with structuralism's focus on linguistic meaning while excluding the various dimensions of meaning conveyed by subjects. As cited by Brandist, Bakhtin stated that "dialectics was born from dialogue in order to return to dialogue at a higher level (a dialogue of personalities)" (p. 168). This suggests that Bakhtin may have preferred the concept of a "dialogic dialectic," which is fundamentally rooted in the interaction between multiple voices, perspectives, and subjects. According to Bakhtin, dialectics is not a monological progression; it begins within dialogue and ultimately returns to it at a "higher level." This "higher level," which he terms a "dialogue of personalities," reflects a more advanced form of interaction in which individuals engage in mutual recognition and development. This underscores Bakhtin's belief that dialectics, in its most authentic form, is an open, ongoing process driven by continuous, dynamic exchanges between participants. In this model, dialectics evolves through dialogue, with each conversation shaping and transforming the others involved.

Nikulin (2010) views dialogue as the foundational origin of dialectic, characterized by spontaneity and unpredictability. However, dialectic aspires to emancipate itself from its foundational origin, seeking to transcend it and efface the remnants of the dialogical within its structure, evolving into a rigorous science and method. While dialogue fosters open-ended exchange and unpredictability, dialectic pertains to the art of probing and debating the veracity of opinions, directed at uncovering latent contradictions and tensions. This relationship underscores a tension where dialectic depends on dialogue for its genesis but seeks independence by prioritizing logical analysis over spontaneity. Thus, dialectic conversation is centered on the synthesis of arguments with the goal of resolving

differences, whereas dialogic conversation seeks to establish a space for reciprocal accommodation without necessarily achieving resolution. In the realm of personal relationships, relational dialectics, as articulated by Baxter and Montgomery (1996), manifests as a uniquely patterned and intricately colored communicative phenomenon. Within this framework, the dialogic complexities inherent in personal communication are woven with common dialectical threads, including contradiction, change, praxis, and totality.

Similarly, in contrast to Bakhtin, who asserts that dialectic reduces voices, emotions, and ideas to a singular abstract consciousness (Rule, 2011), Freire (1970; 1974) posits that dialogue and dialectic are mutually interconnected. True dialogue possesses a dialectical nature, characterized by the interaction of opposing ideas, which can be referred to as dialectical dialogue, essential for the development of critical consciousness. This form of dialogue enables participants to critically examine their social reality, fostering the continuous emergence of new understandings. The ultimate aim of dialectical dialogue is to promote social transformation and emancipation. Praxis, in Freire's philosophy, represents the synthesis of dialectical tension and dialogical engagement, uniting reflection and action for social change. Through dialogue, individuals critically examine their conditions, while the dialectic reveals underlying contradictions, enabling transformative action. Freire's approach weaves these elements together to advocate for an education system that fosters critical consciousness and human liberation, transforming learning into an active, co-creative process that addresses societal inequalities.

In a similar vein, Ravenscroft et al. (2007) argue that dialectic and dialogue, rather than being contradictory, are complementary in nature, each highlighting distinct yet essential aspects of the learning process. They describe dialectic as addressing the cognitive dimension, while dialogue engages the social and emotional facets. Together, these dimensions foster both mutual understanding and the pursuit of reasoned consensus, which are synergistic rather than conflicting. The authors further suggest that the balance between dialectic and dialogue in effective learning depends on the specific context. Similarly, Williams and Ryan (2020) propose that decisions reached through dialectic should not be seen as fixed endpoints but as provisional conclusions subject to practical testing. This iterative process involves ongoing dialogue and subsequent refinement. Dafermos (2018) adds that both dialectical thinking and dialogue are inherently continuous and open-ended processes. As they evolve historically, they create new opportunities for mutual enrichment and sharing, potentially leading to transformative and unpredictable outcomes.

Thus, based on the above discussion, it is obvious that the interrelationship between dialogue and dialectics is grounded in their complementary and symbiotic functions, wherein each enriches the other through a dynamic process of communication and critical engagement. Dialogue serves as a space for individuals to express diverse viewpoints, fostering an open environment for the sharing of perspectives and experiences. Conversely, dialectics provides the structured framework necessary for the critical analysis of these perspectives, aiding individuals in identifying contradictions and reconciling opposing viewpoints, while also allowing for the emergence of new, nuanced understandings. This relationship is integral to meaningful communication and the cultivation of critical thinking. Dialogue establishes the platform for ideas to emerge, whereas dialectics equips individuals with the tools to scrutinize, synthesize, and refine these ideas. Collectively, they facilitate constructive conversations that challenge preconceptions and promote

deeper insights into complex issues. Beyond individual exchanges, this interplay extends into broader social and cultural contexts, where dialogue fosters inclusivity, empathy, and mutual respect, and dialectics encourages the critical examination of social structures, beliefs, and power dynamics, thereby contributing to societal progress and transformation.

This dynamic relationship between dialogue and dialectics enables different voices to emerge, converge, and diverge, thereby expanding the horizons of critical thinking, consciousness, and both individual and social transformation. Dialogue allows for the expression of diverse perspectives, while dialectics provides a framework for evaluating and synthesizing these viewpoints, fostering deeper reflection and the potential for transformation. Through this process, individuals engage with one another in ways that challenge preconceived notions, enhance understanding, and contribute to the rethinking of social structures and norms. Consequently, both personal growth and collective progress are facilitated, with dialogue and dialectics serving as catalysts for the continuous evolution of ideas and social change.

This synthesis between dialogue and dialectics underscores their reciprocal relationship, wherein dialogue facilitates the emergence of ideas, while dialectics offers the critical framework necessary to test, refine, and transform those ideas. This interplay allows for contestation and contradiction, which in turn creates new opportunities for dialogue. Consequently, this symbiotic relationship is essential for the genuine transformation of individuals and their social development.

In educational practices, Bakhtin's theory of dialogism is often associated with dialogic approaches, while Vygotskii's cultural-historical theory aligns more closely with dialectic methods. However, contemporary interpretations of sociocultural theories that draw from Vygotskii's work frequently eschew explicit references to dialectics. There is an ongoing debate regarding the compatibility and irreconcilability of the dialogic and dialectic approaches advocated by thinkers in the context of education. Matusov (2011) is among the scholars who argue for the perceived incompatibility and irreconcilability of Vygotskian and Bakhtinian approaches to education. He posits that Vygotskii's ideas are rooted in Hegelian universalism, characterized by a monological, developmental (diachronic), and activity-based philosophy, whereas Bakhtin's ideas are pluralistic, fundamentally synchronic, dialogic, and centered on discourse and genre-based approaches that embrace the coexistence of competing and conflicting ideas. Matusov further contends that Vygotskii's sociohistorical approach is instrumental, defining consciousness through activity and mediation, while Bakhtin's perspective is ontological, defining consciousness through embodied experience, responsibility, respect, relationships, and dignity. Nonetheless, I contend that this interpretation oversimplifies and inadequately captures the complexities inherent in the contributions of both thinkers.

In contrast, Stetsenko (2007) advocates for the integration of the perspectives of both Vygotskii and Bakhtin, positing that such compatibility can enhance the ethical dimensions of human learning and development. She argues that both scholars advanced a deeply relational understanding of human development and consciousness, fostering an agentive, activist stance toward human life and existence. Both thinkers highlight the process of becoming the emergence of the self ("I") in, with, and through others.

In the subsequent section, I will further explore the perspectives of Bakhtin and Vygotskii, illustrating their interconnections and elucidating how they inform our educational practices and enhance our understanding of what it means to become agentive human beings.

Bakhtinian Dialogue and Vygotskian Dialectic in Education

Both Vygotskii and Bakhtin, as stated by Smolka et al. (1995), share the perspective that human consciousness originates from social communication and undergoes development through internalization. Consciousness is socially and historically constructed; thus, it is the highest form of knowing and learning that emerges through reflection and refraction (Sullivan, 2010). For Vygotskii, consciousness emerges in and through dialectical ways of knowing, while for Bakhtin, it arises in and through dialogue (Sullivan, 2010). However, their divergence lies in their interpretations of dialogism. Vygotskii adopts a dialectical methodology in conceiving phenomena, seeking unification, systematization, and synthesis of multiple voices and consciousnesses. He envisions a rational dialogue leading to a unified view of truth, emphasizing the attainability of general knowledge and universal truth through negotiations and challenges (White, 2014).

In contrast, Bakhtin introduces polyphonic dialogism, asserting the unfinalizable nature of dialogue. Grounded in his observation of Dostoevsky's polyphonic novels, Bakhtin sees human consciousness as continuously evolving, contesting all forms of knowledge and truth without converging on a unified perspective. For Bakhtin, the emphasis is on the perpetual contestation of diverse truths rather than their attainment (White, 2014). However, both scholars emphasize the role of language, dialogue, and interaction for developing self, theoretical or scientific thinking, and transformation of human beings.

Dafermos (2018) notes that dialectically oriented dialogism can be a potent tool for advancing development, particularly in the Zone of Proximal Development (ZPD), where higher-level understanding emerges through collective efforts and negotiations. However, criticisms of Vygotskii emerge, with some scholars arguing that his approach may be adult-centric or ethnocentric due to the unequal status between participants (Matusov, 2011).

Wertsch (1985) points out Vygotskii's focus on individual consciousness at the ontogenetic level, whereas Bakhtin directs attention to the interrelationships among multiple consciousnesses and their sociocultural contexts. This distinction reflects their divergent approaches, with Vygotskii centered on individual cognitive development and Bakhtin exploring the complex interplays of consciousness within broader sociocultural dynamics.

Furthermore, Bakhtin delves into the concept of answerability, emphasizing the responsibility individuals bear in relation to others and to the broader world. Both Bakhtin and Vygotskii posit that human existence in the world is not preordained but necessitates individuals to actively shape their place by taking responsible actions in their interactions with fellow humans and the environment. According to Clark and Holquist (1984), every uttered word not only responds to a past word but also anticipates a future one. The unfinalizable nature of dialogue, as they point out, underscores human potential by representing an ongoing exchange between what already exists (the given) and what is yet to be created (the future).

Nevertheless, as noted by Dafermos (2018), Bakhtin's interpretation of dialectics as dialogism is just one perspective among many. An alternative view sees dialogism as an essential mode of thinking rooted in the fundamental connections between individuals or voices. In this interpretation, the truth or knowledge emerging from dialectical thinking is intricately tied to dialogism, emphasizing the collective and negotiated nature of the process. Different interpretations of dialectics, as suggested by Dafermos, open avenues for diverse perspectives on the interplay between dialogism and the construction of knowledge.

However, Matusov's (2011) comparative analysis of Vygotskii's and Bakhtin's approaches to consciousness offers a thought-provoking perspective that challenges the traditional understanding of these two influential figures in Western Cultural Psychology. Matusov argues that Vygotskii and Bakhtin, rather than espousing similar ideas, actually put forth contrasting conceptions of subjectivity. While both authors posit that individual consciousness is a social product, they do so through different theoretical frameworks. According to Matusov, Vygotskii's approach is characterized by its diachronic, monologic, and activity-based nature, emphasizing the developmental aspect of consciousness and the internalization of social influences as individuals mature. In contrast, Bakhtin's perspective is described as synchronic, dialogic, and discourse-based, highlighting the ongoing interplay of external voices in shaping an individual's consciousness across the lifespan. Matusov's analysis raises important implications for education and pedagogy. He suggests that Vygotskii's view, with its emphasis on the instrumental role of sociality in consciousness, may risk treating children as passive recipients of knowledge rather than active, conscious beings with their own rights and agency. In contrast, Bakhtin's ontological view of consciousness as inherently pluralistic aligns with a pedagogical approach that values and promotes the diverse voices and perspectives of children. Matusov further contends that Vygotskii's approach could be seen as limiting and potentially dehumanizing from Bakhtin's perspective, while Bakhtin's dialogic approach may be viewed as overlooking the developmental aspect of individual consciousness. Ultimately, Matusov concludes that the conceptualizations of Vygotskii and Bakhtin are not only distinct but also irreconcilable.

However, as claimed by Voloshinov (1986, p. 11), for Bakhtin, "consciousness becomes consciousness ... only in the process of social interaction. Individual consciousness is ... [a] tenant lodging in the social edifice of ideological signs" (cited in Rommetveit, 2014, p. 41). For Vygotskii, the "social dimension of consciousness is primary in time and in fact. The individual dimension is derivative and secondary" (Vygotskii, 1979, p. 30, cited in Rommetveit, 2014, p. 41). Vygotskii viewed the relationship between thought and speech as dialectical, with inner speech emerging from the internalization of social dialogue or speech (Vygotskii, 2012). Vygotskii proposed that egocentric speech "turns into" inner speech rather than fading away, demonstrating a dialectical transformation. These statements allude to the possibilities of compatibility, as both Bakhtin and Vygotskii recognize the role of social interaction in developing consciousness. Both thinkers recognize the importance of social interaction and communication in cognitive processes. They view dialogue as a crucial mechanism for the development of thought and consciousness.

Vygotskii and Bakhtin's approaches, despite their differences, complement each other in various ways (Cornejo, 2012). While Vygotskii's model is influenced by Hegel's universalist perspective and highlights the interplay between thinking and speaking, Bakhtin's approach is fundamentally dialogical. Some scholars argue that recognizing the fundamental similarities between Vygotskii

and the Bakhtin circle could have significant implications for educational research, learning, cognition, and development. Despite their differing conceptualizations, both Vygotskii and Bakhtin share beliefs regarding the importance of voice and selfhood in consciousness. This mutual emphasis on certain aspects of human development and cognition allows for a complementary understanding when considering their theories together. Vygotskii's focus on the role of language and culture in cognitive development can be enriched by Bakhtin's emphasis on dialogue and the social nature of language. Similarly, Bakhtin's ideas about the polyphonic nature of language and the dynamic interplay of voices can provide valuable insights into Vygotskii's concept of the zone of proximal development. By integrating these perspectives, researchers and educators can gain a more comprehensive understanding of how language, culture, and social interaction shape cognitive processes and learning experiences. This integrated approach has the potential to inform educational practices that are more attuned to the diverse linguistic and cultural backgrounds of learners, ultimately enhancing the effectiveness of instruction and promoting equitable educational opportunities for all students.

In my opinion, Vygotskii's conceptualization of consciousness is rooted in psychology, underscoring the social dimension of development and the significant role of the *cultural-historical unfolding* of knowledge in its formation. Conversely, Bakhtin's perspective adopts a linguistic approach, accentuating the dialogical nature of consciousness as shaped by social interactions and communicative exchanges. While Vygotskii prioritizes the interplay between knowledge acquisition and social interactions as pivotal in molding consciousness, Bakhtin's framework centers on the dynamic and interactive aspects of consciousness, where individuals actively participate in dialogue to construct their understanding of the world. These contrasting perspectives reflect distinct philosophical orientations towards the genesis and evolution of agentive becoming and human consciousness. It is noteworthy that psychology devoid of language and language bereft of psychology are inconceivable, as cognitive development relies on the social and communicative functions of speech, and language itself is shaped by individual thought processes. Together, their theories reveal that speech serves not only as a tool for individual cognition but also as a medium for collective meaning-making, enriching learning in both personal and social dimensions. Therefore, Vygotskii considers speech as one of the higher psychological functions and resources for recreating and restructuring human consciousness (Veresov, 2021), while Bakhtin may consider critical dialogue as a source of authorial agency and consciousness. Critical dialogue is inherently dialectical, as it involves problem identification, problem-solving, and problem-posing (Freire, 1974).

By synthesizing the perspectives of Vygotskii and Bakhtin, one can discern a shared focus on the profound interconnection between psychology and language in the formation of human consciousness. Both theoretical frameworks underscore the dual functions of speech: as a cognitive resource, and as a social conduit. As a cognitive resource, speech empowers individuals to internalize and organize their thoughts, thereby facilitating personal understanding and fostering intellectual growth. Concurrently, as a social conduit, it enables interaction, dialogue, and the co-construction of meaning, thus enhancing collective meaning-making processes. This dynamic interplay between individual cognition and social interaction enriches both personal development and communal learning experiences, illustrating the inseparability of the psychological and linguistic dimensions in human learning, intellectual development, and agentive becoming.

However, a significant question arises regarding dialogue and dialectic in the era of generative AI tools, which facilitate continuous dialogue and interaction as long as we have access to effective electronic communication systems. These AI tools allow for inquiries and discussions on a wide range of topics and issues. They often appear omniscient, capable of responding to any query, and we can engage with them in infinite dialogue and dialectic, although the accuracy of their answers may be questionable. Ironically, AI tools do not comprehend words or sentences in the same manner that humans do; nevertheless, they possess the ability to generate responses and sometimes produce complex and intriguing ideas. Thus, what kind of dialogue and dialectic can we establish (if we can) with AI tools such as ChatGPT? Is it possible to engage in a genuine dialogue with them? Furthermore, can we engage dialectically with these systems? What implications might interactions with artificial tools hold for education, as well as for our learning and intellectual development? This following section explores and discusses the onto-epistemological implications of these tools within the context of higher education.

Artificial Intelligence and the Nature of Dialogue and Dialectic

Hegel's concept of dialectical logic characterizes systems by their components and by the nature of the connections between them. In his work "Phenomenology of Spirit" (Hegel, 2018), Hegel distinguishes between mechanical systems and organic (or living) systems, each exhibiting distinct characteristics. In mechanical systems, all components exist simultaneously and are connected externally, interacting in fixed, causal manners. Conversely, organic systems are dynamic; their components undergo development, growth, and differentiation over time. In this paradigm, the entire system generates its components, which Hegel refers to as "organs of the system," and these components are interrelated through the holistic functioning of the system. For instance, Veresov (2021) contrasts a car engine, where all components interact mechanically, with a tree, which organically grows branches that sprout smaller branches over time. This distinction underscores the shift from rigid, external causality in mechanical systems to reciprocal, purposive unity in organic systems.

Hegel's mechanical dialectic pertains to inorganic, external processes, governed by contingent causality and devoid of internal purpose. Relationships within such systems are defined by external interactions, as exemplified by the functioning of a machine. In contrast, the organic dialectic introduces self-determination and internal unity, wherein contradictions within the system propel its development. Living systems exemplify this, as the interdependence between parts and the whole engenders a dynamic, evolving unity. This dialectical progression—from mechanical to organic—reflects Hegel's broader philosophical framework, culminating in the self-realization of spirit (*Geist*). Within this context, spirit represents the ultimate stage of development, in which systems achieve freedom and self-consciousness through internal contradictions and holistic unity.

When metaphorically applying Hegel's framework to AI systems, one might contend that AI resembles a mechanical system. Essential infrastructures—such as electricity, internet connectivity, and devices like smartphones or computers—must be present for AI to operate effectively. These infrastructures interact in fixed, external ways, analogous to the components of a machine. Furthermore, enhancements in speed, computational power, and data quality augment the efficacy of AI communication, underscoring the mechanical nature of its evolution. Unlike

organic systems, AI systems lack inherent self-determination or internal unity; their development is contingent upon external forces and infrastructures.

Hegel's dialectical logic, whether applied to natural or technological systems, emphasizes the dynamic interplay between parts and wholes. While mechanical systems demonstrate foundational yet static interrelations, organic systems represent a higher stage of complexity, characterized by internal purpose and holistic development. This distinction not only provides a framework for understanding living systems and human consciousness, but also offers insights into the limitations of contemporary technological systems such as AI, which remain bound by external dependencies and mechanical causality.

Consequently, AI systems are best understood through the lens of Hegel's mechanical dialectic, as their operation depends significantly on external infrastructures and fixed, contingent relationships. These systems lack the self-determination and internal unity characteristic of organic dialectics, instead relying on human actors to design, train, and refine them. The quality of AI output is directly correlated with the knowledge and intelligence of human developers, as well as the data and algorithms they employ. Human actors provide the foundational inputs—ranging from computational frameworks to ethical considerations—upon which AI systems operate. This dependency reinforces the mechanical nature of AI systems, where progress and efficiency are externally imposed rather than internally driven. Consequently, the potential of AI is constrained by the intelligence and expertise of its creators, underscoring its status as a contingent, mechanical construct within the broader dialectical framework.

Thus, ontologically, understanding AI systems through Hegel's mechanical dialectic suggests that these systems exist as external, contingent entities, lacking intrinsic purpose or self-determination. AI systems do not possess an independent self and agency; they function only within a network of human-constructed infrastructures, such as electricity, internet connectivity, and computational resources. Their "being" is defined entirely by their relationships with external factors and their capacity to perform tasks dictated by human actors. Ontologically, this positions AI as a tool—a highly complex and efficient one—but not as a self-contained entity capable of evolving or self-realizing in the way organic systems can. The existence and extinction of AI systems are socio-political decisions, shaped by human priorities and governance, rather than natural processes.

In Martin Buber's (1944) dialogic philosophy, there are three main types of relationships that shape human interactions: the *I-It* relationship, the *I-Thou* relationship, and the *I-You* relationship. The *I-It* relationship is defined by one party treating the other as an object or a tool, rather than as a subject with its own consciousness and internal life. This relationship is utilitarian and functional, with the "It" being something to be used, manipulated, or observed, rather than engaged with. The *I-Thou* relationship, in contrast, is a reciprocal and transformative exchange in which both parties recognize each other as subjects with unique internal lives. There is a mutual, subjective engagement, and the interaction is marked by a deep, meaningful connection that goes beyond mere utility. The *I-You* relationship lies somewhere in between, involving mutual recognition of the other as a human being, but without the same level of depth or transformation as is seen in the *I-Thou* relationship.

When comparing AI dialogue to Buber's *I-It* relationship, we see that AI fits squarely into this category. In interactions with AI, the human user treats the AI as a tool or instrument, rather than as a subject. AI is programmed to respond to input data based on pre-set algorithms, but it does not possess subjectivity, self-awareness, or an internal life. The interaction is one-sided and functional, with no mutual recognition or reciprocal engagement. AI is not a participant in the dialogue, but merely an object that provides responses according to its programming. This interaction is not transformative or meaningful in the way Buber's *I-Thou* relationship is; the AI remains a mechanical entity, devoid of consciousness, that responds mechanically to inputs without understanding or adapting to the deeper meaning or emotional dynamics of the conversation.

Recent studies (Matusov et al., 2024) suggest that while AI lacks a dialogical self, it may possess a discursive self (referring to Hermans, 2022). A dialogical self is characterized by personal "I-positions" that engage in subjective, multivocal, and context-sensitive interactions, rooted in identity, selfhood, and consciousness. In contrast, a discursive self refers to impersonal "objectified it-positions," devoid of personal subjectivity and self-reflection. These "it-positions" represent external influences on the self, such as societal norms, institutional discourses, or predefined roles, rather than personal, dialogical engagement. However, the question of whether AI tools possess any form of self remains debatable, as the concept of self is often considered exclusive to human beings. AI might be more accurately described as a discursive tool that responds to inquiries and prompts. It does not possess any self or subjectivity, which is manifest in onto-epistemological perspectiveness and 'mineness' of experiences (Northoff & Gouveia, 2024). This raises questions that warrant broader philosophical discussion and debate.

Nonetheless, AI appears to embody aspects of *demosophia*, a philosophical concept coined by Christakis (2014), which combines the Greek words *demos* (the people) and *sophia* (wisdom), meaning "*the wisdom of the people.*" This concept is rooted in democratic ideals of inclusivity, dialogue, and collaboration, where collective input from diverse individuals contributes to more informed, equitable, and sustainable solutions to societal challenges. AI systems can present the idea of collective wisdom by synthesizing shared knowledge, experiences, and facts from diverse digital landscapes. Additionally, the multimodal capabilities of AI enable dialogue with users across various contexts, including those with physical impairments. Its dialogic nature—marked by iterative exchanges—can foster collective creativity and decision-making processes that transcend geographical, cultural, and disciplinary boundaries.

Critically, AI systems reflect the political power structures that determine how ideas are organized, structured, and disseminated. From this perspective, AI can perpetuate systemic biases, leading, as Noble (2018) describes it, to an "*algorithm of oppression.*" AI does not operate in isolation; its training datasets are rooted in social contexts rife with power imbalances and historical injustices. The historical misuse of science to categorize, rank, and exclude individuals based on arbitrary traits echoes in modern AI systems. These systems risk normalizing exclusionary practices by propagating knowledge that often mirrors the perspectives of dominant groups, marginalizing or distorting the voices of minority communities. For instance, algorithms trained on biased datasets can reinforce stereotypes, exclude underrepresented narratives, and reproduce inequities in access to resources. Research has shown that AI detectors may flag non-native English speakers' writings as AI-generated (Liang et al., 2023), raising concerns about the perpetuation of prejudices against

certain communities. This phenomenon underscores how AI, while promising inclusivity, can inadvertently reinforce existing hierarchies and systemic inequities.

Engaging in dialogue with AI systems embedded within superstructures of fixed ideologies presents complex risks that can undermine social understanding and cohesion. These systems are often shaped by the dominant narratives and epistemologies present in their training data, which may unintentionally prioritize mainstream or widely accepted perspectives while marginalizing alternative or critical viewpoints. Consequently, they risk reinforcing homogeneous ways of understanding social issues, thereby limiting the scope of inquiry and suppressing the plurality of voices essential for a well-rounded discourse. This dynamic fosters echo chambering (Sharma et al., 2024), wherein users are continually exposed to ideas that align with their existing beliefs, and epistemic bubbles. Over time, such feedback loops can amplify biases and cultivate an environment where extreme positions are normalized, diminishing the space for critical engagement and nuanced dialogue. As Nguyen (2020) argues, echo chambers are more deliberate and insidious structures wherein dissenting perspectives are actively discredited and excluded. Within echo chambers, members are conditioned to systematically distrust external sources, leading to a self-reinforcing cycle that solidifies existing beliefs and entrenches biases. Thus, breaking out of an echo chamber frequently necessitates a profound and intentional re-evaluation of deeply held beliefs, a process sometimes described as “radical rebooting.” Epistemic bubbles as socio-techno social structures in which certain voices or viewpoints are unintentionally excluded, often as a result of the incidental dynamics of social networks or algorithms, thereby creating an incomplete epistemic landscape (Nguyen, 2020), may be addressed easily by addressing algorithmic issues.

Furthermore, the algorithmic tendency to curate information based on user behavior can exacerbate ideological divides, as individuals are increasingly unlikely to encounter perspectives that challenge or broaden their understanding. This erosion of pluralistic dialogue not only perpetuates misunderstandings but also intensifies social fissures, increasing the risk of hostility between groups with divergent viewpoints. Marginalized communities, whose perspectives may already be underrepresented in mainstream narratives, are particularly susceptible to being further sidelined in AI-mediated interactions. This can reinforce feelings of exclusion and alienation, fueling discontent and polarization.

To conclude, echo chambers and epistemic bubbles represent significant threats to the integrity of ethical, fair, just, and inclusive dialogue and dialectic. By selectively filtering or actively discrediting diverse perspectives, these phenomena create environments in which individuals are insulated from opposing viewpoints and critical engagement. In epistemic bubbles, the unintentional exclusion of relevant voices limits exposure to the plurality of ideas necessary for fair and balanced discourse. Echo chambers exacerbate this issue by fostering systematic distrust of external perspectives, actively undermining the legitimacy of alternative viewpoints. This dynamic not only distorts the flow of information, but also entrenches biases, perpetuates misinformation, and reinforces ideological divides.

The implications for dialogue and dialectic are profound. In ethical and inclusive exchanges, all participants must have equitable opportunities to share and critically evaluate ideas. However, echo chambers erode this foundation by promoting homogeneity and suppressing dissent. This

undermines fairness, as certain voices are delegitimized or excluded, as may be justice, as marginalized perspectives are systematically silenced. Without genuine engagement across diverse viewpoints, the dialectic process of synthesizing new understandings through critical examination becomes impossible. Instead, the cycle of self-reinforcement within these structures perpetuates polarization and hostility, further fracturing societal cohesion.

To counteract these challenges, it is important to dismantle the conditions that sustain echo chambers and epistemic bubbles. This includes fostering pluralistic dialogue by promoting diverse, credible perspectives and developing educational initiatives that equip individuals with critical media literacy skills. Additionally, creating spaces for equitable participation and deliberation can help rebuild trust and bridge divides. By addressing these epistemic challenges, society can work towards a model of dialogue and dialectic that upholds the principles of ethics, fairness, justice, and inclusivity, which are essential for navigating the complexities of a pluralistic and interconnected world.

Conclusion

Dialogue and dialectic are inherently interdependent, and exploring this symbiotic relationship offers transformative potential for advancing intellectual development in higher education. As foundational processes of human intellectual becoming, dialogue and dialectic shape the way we engage with the world, with others, and with ourselves. Whether addressing personal or professional concerns, we initiate dialogue with those closest to us. In this way, every attempt to develop a shared understanding of issues, events, and concerns is dialectical in nature. This understanding is never final or absolute; it is always provisional, subject to modification as new information emerges, thus opening avenues for further dialogue. Meaning making is, therefore, an ongoing, multi-voiced process, a series of dialectical moments where ideas and perspectives are organized, scrutinized, and synthesized. This unfinalizable process generates continuous dialogue, leading to an evolving consciousness and an ever-developing mechanism of intellectual advancement.

Both dialogue and dialectic are aimed at fostering higher levels of human thinking and intellectual maturity. However, the true potential of higher education lies in exploring and nurturing their symbiotic relationship. This creates spaces and tools for diverse, dynamic meaning-making activities, particularly in the context of democratic development and academic freedom. A healthy symbiosis between dialogue and dialectic provides the necessary conditions for impartial and evidence-based debate on any idea, issue, or concern. However, this openness can be threatened by political or ideological forces, as superstructures may view such organic discussion as uncomfortable or destabilizing.

Likewise, AI systems have the potential to serve as tools that extend the spaces and tools of dialogue and dialectic. By assisting with the exploration, organization, and structuring of ideas, AI can expand the possibilities for discourse and inquiry. However, AI cannot truly replicate the essence of human dialogue and dialectic, which is grounded in complex socio-cultural and psychological processes. These processes are integral to constructing selfhood, agency, and personhood, all of which are unique to human interaction. AI, lacking consciousness and emotional depth, cannot engage in the relational, social, and collaborative nature of human

learning. While AI-generated knowledge can be valuable when prompted appropriately, it risks reinforcing the passive, one-way model of education where knowledge is received rather than actively constructed. Additionally, AI tools could facilitate unethical academic practices such as cheating, plagiarism, and deepfakes, undermining the epistemological integrity of education.

Given these risks, it is crucial to reframe teaching and learning practices to ensure that AI supports, rather than replaces, the dynamic, critical, and collaborative processes of human learning. Higher education institutions must adopt problem-based, collaborative approaches that leverage AI's capabilities in areas where it excels while preserving the irreplaceable human aspects of education. As AI increasingly performs tasks such as creating lesson plans or generating assignments, there is a need to rethink traditional pedagogical models. This redesign must involve collective dialogue and dialectic between educators, AI developers, and learners to ensure that AI is used ethically and effectively in education. Embracing this paradigm shift will enable institutions to adapt to the evolving educational landscape, fostering a more authentic, ethical, and intellectually enriching environment for all.

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